

PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE'S INFLUENCE ON MODERN CULTURE IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION

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ABSTRACT: The scientific article provides a philosophical analysis of the influence of artificial intelligence on literature in the era of globalization. It examines how artificial intelligence technologies transform literary creativity, change the roles of the author and reader, and also influence the content and forms of works. Particular attention is paid to issues of authorship, creativity and originality in the context of the active use of artificial intelligence. The article discusses the ethical and philosophical dilemmas associated with the use of artificial intelligence in literature, including questions about the future of human creativity and the possibilities for preserving cultural heritage.

Keywords: philosophy, ethics, literature, globalization, artificial intelligence, copyright, text generation, text analysis, personalization, creative process.

ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ВЛИЯНИЯ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА НА СОВРЕМЕННУЮ КУЛЬТУРУ В КОНТЕКСТЕ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ

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АННОТАЦИЯ: В научной статье представлен философский анализ влияния искусственного интеллекта на литературу в эпоху глобализации. Рассматривается, как технологии искусственного интеллекта трансформируют литературное творчество, меняют роли автора и читателя, а также воздействуют на содержание и формы произведений. Особое внимание уделено вопросам авторства, творчества и оригинальности в контексте активного использования искусственного интеллекта. В статье обсуждаются этические и философские дилеммы, связанные с применением искусственного интеллекта в литературе, включая вопросы о будущем человеческого творчества и возможностях сохранения культурного наследия.

Ключевые слова: философия, этика, литература, глобализация, искусственный интеллект, авторское право, генерация текста, анализ текста, персонализация, творческий процесс.

Introduction

Modern literature is in constant interaction with technology, reflecting its impact on society and human experience. Online publishing platforms, social networks, and e-mail

books have significantly changed the ways of disseminating and perceiving literature. Technology also influences the writing process itself, providing creators with new tools and opportunities for creativity.

Artificial intelligence is a field of informatics that deals with creating systems capable of performing tasks requiring human intelligence, and also includes various methods and technologies such as machine learning, natural language processing, neural networks, and others.

The application of artificial intelligence covers many areas of activity, including medicine, economics, energy, industry, education, literature, communications, entertainment, and others.

Studying the impact of artificial intelligence on modern literature is a multifaceted topic that encompasses various aspects, from text creation to the analysis and promotion of literature.

This article aims to conduct a philosophical analysis of the influence of artificial intelligence on modern literature, exploring both the technical and conceptual aspects of this phenomenon. In particular, how the interaction between man and machine is changing traditional ideas about literary creativity, and what prospects are opening up for literature in the era of artificial intelligence. Philosophical analysis will help not only to better understand current changes but also to chart paths for further research in the fields of philosophy, literature, and technology.

Literature review and research methodology

The role of artificial intelligence in the development of modern literature is an exciting and relevant research topic. Let's start with the fact that artificial intelligence is no longer limited to the fields of technology and computer science. It actively influences various aspects of human life, including culture and art, including literature.

Artificial intelligence in modern literature can perform a number of functions:

Text generation. Using deep learning algorithms such as recurrent neural networks and transformers, texts are created that can imitate the style and themes of literary works. This can range from generating poetry to writing novels [1].

Text analysis. Artificial intelligence-based text analysis algorithms can help identify trends, themes, and styles in literature, allowing authors and researchers to gain new approaches to analyzing literary works [2].

Personalization and recommendations. Recommendation systems based on artificial intelligence help readers find works that best match their preferences and interests, thereby improving the user's reading experience [3].

Creating interactive and animated stories. Artificial intelligence is used to create interactive texts where the reader can influence the development of the plot, as well as

for developing animated stories where characters act in accordance with artificial intelligence algorithms [4].

Assistance in the creative process. Some writers use AI-based tools to help them write, edit, and develop their ideas, which can include generating ideas, correcting grammatical errors, and analyzing the text for structural or stylistic issues.

According to a study by Grammarly (an artificial intelligence-based online platform for assisting in English language communication), texts created by artificial intelligence can contain up to 5-10% of grammatical errors, depending on the text's complexity and the model's training

level [5]. Stylistic errors occur less frequently, about 3-7%, as modern models such as GPT-3 and GPT-4 are sufficiently well-trained on diverse data corpora [6]. Semantic errors vary depending on the specific task. For example, in machine translation tasks, accuracy can reach 80-85%, which means that about 15-20% of translations may contain semantic errors [7].

However, despite all the listed advantages, there are also certain problems associated with using artificial intelligence in literature, which include copyright issues, ethical aspects of using generative text models, and preserving originality and creativity in the literary process. Researching the use of artificial intelligence in literature through philosophical methods requires a comprehensive approach that unites

various branches of philosophy:

Ontology. Researching the essence of artificial intelligence in the context of literature. This method helps to understand how artificial intelligence interacts with literary reality, how it perceives and interprets texts, and how it influences the understanding of literary history and cultural heritage [8].

Ethics. Philosophical analysis of ethical issues includes issues of algorithm transparency, text authorship, bias and justice, as well as the impact on cultural values and public consciousness [9].

Epistemology. Researching the processes of cognition and understanding of texts created with the participation of artificial intelligence helps to understand how artificial intelligence perceives and analyzes texts, how it creates new knowledge and interpretations, and how it influences epistemological practice and confidence in the truth of knowledge [10].

Philosophy of technology. Analyzing the impact of technology on literature and cultural development allows for researching how the use of artificial intelligence in literature changes perceptions of creativity, authorship, reading, and literary criticism, as well as what new opportunities and challenges it presents for the literary world [11].

Artificial Intelligence Philosophy. Considering fundamental issues allows for understanding which philosophical principles underlie the development and use of artificial intelligence in literature, as well as which ethical and cultural aspects should be considered when implementing these technologies [12].

Using these philosophical methods allows for a deep and comprehensive understanding of the influence of artificial intelligence on literature, as well as posing key questions aimed at developing this research field.

Research results

The use of artificial intelligence in modern literature represents a unique research field that combines traditional literary approaches with advanced technologies. Let us provide an overview of the main research results in this field:

Automatically generate text focus on developing deep learning algorithms and models capable of generating texts that can be described as literary. Examples include models based on recurrent neural networks or transformers that can create poetry, stories, and even novels.

Text analysis using artificial intelligence methods, focuses on analyzing existing literature. Natural language processing methods allow for the identification of themes, structures, and styles in texts, which helps researchers better understand literary works and trends in literature.

Developing tools for authors and critics aimed at creating software tools that can help writers in the creative process or critics in analyzing texts. These tools can include idea generators, tools for checking stylistic similarity with famous authors, or algorithms for automatically assessing literary quality.

Ethical issues. With the development of artificial intelligence technologies, ethical issues arise related to its use in literature and the analysis of copyright issues, transparency in text creation, and the impact of automatically created works on cultural norms and values..

Interactive literary projects. The use of artificial intelligence also opens up new opportunities for interactive literature. Projects that combine text and artificial intelligence technologies allow readers to interact with works, change plotlines, or even influence character traits.

These research results represent only a small part of the vast world of interaction between artificial intelligence and literature. Together, they demonstrate that the use of artificial intelligence in literature not only expands the boundaries of creativity but also creates new opportunities for analyzing and understanding textual works.

The influence of artificial intelligence on the literary and tourist environment leads to several noticeable changes:

Automation of writing processes. With the emergence of generative models such as GPT, authors can use them to create texts faster and more effectively, which leads to an increase in the volume of works, but also raises questions about authorship and originality.

Personalized reading. Artificial intelligence allows for the creation of personalized recommendations for readers based on their preferences and reading history, which changes the way people discover new books and authors, making the process more convenient and engaging.

Analytics and editing. Algorithms can be used to analyze texts for stylistic errors, inconsistencies, and other aspects, which helps editors and writers improve text quality and make editing more effective.

Copyright and piracy. With the development of artificial intelligence technologies, new challenges are emerging in the field of copyright protection and the fight against piracy. Authors and publishers must adapt and use new methods to protect their works.

Experiments with genres and styles. Generative models facilitate experiments with genres and styles. Authors can use artificial intelligence to create texts that transcend traditional literary genres and approaches.

The impact of artificial intelligence on the literary and tourism environment represents a mixed set of opportunities and challenges that require careful consideration and discussion by both writers and publishers, as well as readers and researchers.

Discussion of research results Discussing the impact of artificial intelligence on the quality, accessibility, and structure of literature reveals many interesting points of view..

Quality of literature. Artificial intelligence can help improve the quality of literature by providing writers with tools for text analysis, suggestions on style, syntax, and even plot. This can contribute to the emergence of new, more original works, as well as help authors improve their skills.

Availability of literature. Optical character recognition and automatic translation technologies allow for scanning and translating texts into various languages, making literary works accessible to a wider audience, including people with disabilities.

Structure of literature . Algorithms can analyze reader preferences and offer personalized recommendations, which can influence the selection and distribution of literary works. Artificial intelligence can also be used to create new literary formats, such as interactive books or generative texts.

However, it should be remembered that the influence of artificial intelligence on literature also carries its own risks. For example, with the increasing automation of text writing processes,

there is a danger of losing the originality and artistic value of works, as well as the possibility of copyright issues and ethical issues associated with using artificial intelligence to create content.

Conclusion

The impact of artificial intelligence on modern literature is a complex and multi-layered phenomenon that requires deep philosophical analysis. Within the framework of this article, we examined the main aspects of the interaction between artificial intelligence and literary creativity.

Artificial intelligence is significantly transforming the role of the author, providing new tools for text creation. Algorithms can generate plots, styles, and even entire works that

raises questions about the nature of authorship and originality. Modern authors are beginning to work in tandem with artificial intelligence, creating hybrid texts where the boundaries between human and machine creativity are becoming increasingly blurred [13].

Issues of copyright, content responsibility, and the moral aspects of interaction with artificial intelligence are becoming increasingly relevant in light of the development of new technologies. An important aspect here is discussing whether artificial intelligence can create a work equal in depth and significance to human creativity, and how to evaluate such works.

Thus, a philosophical analysis of the impact of artificial intelligence on modern literature demonstrates that this interaction opens up both new opportunities and raises numerous questions requiring further research. Artificial intelligence not only expands the boundaries of what is possible in literature but also forces us to revise the fundamental concepts of creativity, authorship, and reader experience. Ultimately, it is these changes that can lead to new forms of literary art and a deeper understanding of human creativity in the era of technological innovation.

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